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IN VITRO STUDIES ON PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF *PLEUROTUS FLORIDA* CULTIVATED ON PADDY STRAW

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ABSTRACT

Mushrooms are white rot fungi regarded as one of the well known food and possessing various kinds of biopharmaceuticals compounds. Mushrooms are superior to many vegetables based on their nutritional value and it contains 40 - 49% of proteins. The present study consolidates in the aspects of cultivation of *Pleurotus florida* mushroom with phytochemical analysis. *Pleurotus florida* mushroom was cultivated by using paddy straw. Oyster mushroom accounted for 14.2% of the total world production of edible mushroom. *P. florida* was successfully grown on PDA. The fresh fruit bodies of mushroom were harvested, dried, powdered and extracted (by using ethanol) using soxhlate apparatus. The phytochemical characters of *Pleurotus florida* of water and ethanol extract investigated. The aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found to contain alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids and cardiac glycosides. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* showed, the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins and steroids. Aqueous, ethanolic and methanolic extracts contains high amount of phenolic compounds, glycosides and flavonoids based on the phytochemical screening. CONCLUSION: In the present investigation was carried out on cultivation of *Pleurotus florida* and screening of preliminary phytochemicals. *Pleurotus florida* was cultivated on sterilized paddy straw. Environmental factors of pH (6.5) and temperature (25– 30°C) were maintained between mycelia growth to attain harvesting stage. Cultivation of the growth was observed in raw materials in 18-25 days and first harvest can be made on 19th day itself it implies that the growth of the mushroom. Total yield was one kg for one bed. Preliminary phytochemical compounds were screened of *Pleurotus florida* with different extract of aqueous and ethanol solvent. Alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids and cardiac glycosides were presence in aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida*. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* was contain alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins and steroids. Some phytochemical ingredients Phenols, tannins, phlobatannins and anthroquinones were absence in both extracts. Further study can be aimed at to identify the bioactive compounds and determine the cultivation of *Pleurotus florida* on paddy Straw.

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INTRODUCTION

Mushroom are the most conspicuous structures of the fungi world. Mushroom is a fleshy, spore bearing fruiting body of fungi, typically produced above ground on soil or on its food source. Mushroom belongs to phylum Basidiomycota and some of them in the Ascomycota are known as the higher fungi (Moradali *et al.*, 2007; Sicoli *et al.*, 2005). Mushroom farmers use sawdust and rice straw to cultivate edible mushrooms in order to augment food production and generate additional income for the family while the fibrous mushroom substrate produced from mushroom cultivation is usually discarded. The excellent properties of fungi can be exploited for the benefit of the livestock animals (Punnapayak *et al.*, 2007). The first commercial cultivation of edible mushrooms was developed in France in the 18th century (Karthika and Murugesan, 2015). India produces nearly 140 million tones of cereals and equal amount of straw is generated by the farmers, which can partly be utilized by the farmers for mushroom cultivation. Land requirement is a minimum and any spare room of the house can be converted into a mushroom growing room, or a hut built on a piece of land can also be used for the purpose (Subbulakshmi and Kannan, 2016). Mushroom is a non-traditional horticulture crop having high quality of proteins, high fibre value, vitamins and minerals. World produces 61.16 lakh of cultivated mushroom annually (Narayanasamy *et al.*, 2008). Infusion of mushrooms has been used to prevent beriberi. In addition, the decoction has been used for the treatment of abscesses and wounds (Yu *et al.*, 2009). Also it is well known that the incidence of diabetes mellitus is high all over the world, especially in Asia (Rajeshkumar Gupta *et al.*, 2005). Mushrooms also contain polysaccharide present in fruiting bodies and uncultured mycelium that prevent on cogenesis show direct antitumor activity against various all organic and syngenic tumors and prevent tumor metastasis (Wasser, 2012). These are the members of the family both Ascomycotina and Basidiomycotina. Mushrooms are comprised of around 230 genera and 5000 species. Of these more than 2000 species are reported to be edible throughout the world and about 283 of these are reported to be available in India. The main by products used for substrate preparation for mushroom farming is a. wheat / paddy straw, b. sugarcane baggage, c. saw dust, d. Cotton seed meal/soybean meals (Subbulakshmi and kannan, 2016). They can easily grow on almost all types of cellulosic residues such as banana leaves, dried paddy straws (Reyes *et al.*, 1997), cotton waste and rice straws (Fasidi *et al.*, 1993), sawdust enriched with poultry dropping (Onuoha *et al.*, 2014). Oyster mushrooms are one of the most popular edible mushrooms and belong to the genus *pleurotus* and the family Pleurotaceae (Kong *et al.*, 2004).

Phytochemical which are present in the human diets possess a number of beneficial effects on human health. Mushrooms are invaluable sources of useful therapeutic agents (Pandimeena *et al.*, 2015). This mushroom has unique flavor, rich nutrients and phytochemicals. Phytochemical are naturally occurring compounds that works with nutrients to act against diseases or more specifically provides protection against diseases (Mizuno *et al.*, 1995). Oyster mushrooms are also reported to be a rich source of phenolics, alkaloids and flavonoids and are responsible for anti-helminthic activity (Ganeshpurkar *et al.*, 2012). Phytochemical in food materials and their effects on health, especially the suppression of active oxygen species by natural antioxidants from tea, species and herbs have been extensively studied (Ho *et al.*, 1994).

Phytochemical screening of ethanolic and aqueous extracts showed the presence of secondary metabolites such as alkaloid, glycosides, saponin, tannin, flavonoid, reducing compound, polyphenol, but not phlobatannin, anthraquinone and hydroxymethyl anthraquinone (Edet *et al.*, 2016). The present work investigates the influence of different cereal straws and straw supplementations with levels of organic manures on the presence and quantity of some of the phytochemicals compounds in the fruit-bodies of *P. florida*. Free radicals damage tissues and contribute to ageing and degenerate disease (Mitchell, 2003).

OBJECTIVES

- To cultivated the edible mushroom of *Pleurotus florida* on paddy straw
- To harvest the *Pleurotus florida*
- To prepared different solvent (ethanol and Aqueous) of extracts from *Pleurotus florida*
- To screen the phytochemicals of *Pleurotus florida*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Spawn Collection:

In the present study *Pleurotus florida* strain isolated from samples obtained from Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (T.N.A.U), Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India and maintained at 25⁰C. The mycelia form of colonies of different strains was maintained on PDA medium where inoculated in to 100 ml potato dextrose broth contained in 250 ml conical flask. After four weeks growth to the fungus in the liquid medium were observed. Another type of cultures were maintained from petriplates and test-tubes are used in the culture was maintained potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium.

MUSHROOM CULTIVATION

Culture Media:

The mushroom strains can be maintained in semi synthetic solid medium. Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) is the most commonly used media for maintaining the inoculums and they showed good growth rate.

Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) Medium Composition

Dextrose 20.00g Peeled Potato pieces 250.00g Agar 20.00g Distilled water 1000 ml PH 7.0 to 0.2.

Procedure

About 250gms of Potato tubers were washed, peeled off, cut into small species and taken in a 500 ml conical flask containing 300ml of water. It was boiled for about half an hour and the extract was decanted. About 18gm of agar shreds were weighted, taken in another conical flask and 500ml of distilled water was added. The agar was melted over a heater. The molten agar was then mixed with the potato extract and made up to 1 liter. Then 15gm of dextrose was added to the medium and mixed thoroughly. Since the growth of the fungus is favored by acidic range the pH was adjusted to 5-6. The medium was distributed in 250ml conical flask plugged with cotton and sterilized in an autoclave. To avoid bacterial growth streptomycin sulphate was added.

Sterilization Methods

Prior to the use, all glassware and other apparatuses should be sterilized, so that any kind of contamination may be avoided. The sterilization can be made by the following three ways.

Chemical Sterilization

The glassware should be cleaned with detergent first and then with chromic acid. Following Chromic acid, the glassware should be cleaned thoroughly several times with sterile distilled water. The utensils (glassware) should be dried by keeping them in hot air oven.

Dry-Heat Sterilization

By this method the instruments could be sterilized effectively. The scalpels, inoculation needles, glass rods, platinum wire loops etc, could be dipped in rectified spirit, and then heating them over the flame of a spirit lamp or a burner. On the other hand the glassware and other instruments may be sterilized by keeping them in hot air oven at 130°C for 1 hour.

Wet- Heat Sterilization

This is more reliable method for sterilization of media. The prepared medium should be poured either in rimless culture tubes or in flasks, and then plugged their cotton. All these things are placed in a steel wire basket and kept in autoclave at 15 lbs. for 15 to 20 minutes pressure.

Culturing Of *Pleurotus Mycelium* on Petriplates

Inoculation Technique

The sterilized bottles are placed in the culture room. The UV lamp is switched on for 15 minutes to sterilize the air inside and then surface was cleaned using alcohol to ensure axenicity before the use. The growing edge of the fungus from Petri plate was cut with the help of a cork borer and transferred to the spawn bottle in front of the flame. The bottles are incubated at room temperature. The white mycelium is observed in the entire bottle after 12 days of inoculation. This is known as 'mother spawn'.

Substrates

Mushroom beds can be prepared using Paddy straw substrates. One spawn bottle can be used to prepare two beds. Size of the bed should be about 30×60 cm.

Bed Preparation

Fresh paddy straw are chopped into pieces of 2-3 inches length and soaked in water for 10 hours. Water is then drained off from the paddy straw. Afterwards, the paddy straws are sterilized using vertical autoclave at 15 lbs pressure for 20 minutes. The sterilized paddy straws are placed on a wire mesh net for draining excess water. Polythene covers in the size of 30×60cm are procured and filled with the treated paddy straw as follows. Before preparing mushroom beds hands and all the instruments should be sterilized with a dilute solution of KMnO_4 / alcohol. A polythene bag is tied at one end and sterilized paddy straw is filled through the open end for about 5cm in length. A handful of spawn from the bottle is spread (15g) towards the periphery of this layer. Over the spawn some more paddy straw are put and pressed lightly. This process is repeated five times. The mouth of the bag is rolled and closed with stapler pins. Holes are made over the bag for aeration. Inoculated paddy straw bags are kept in a ventilation dark chamber. The mycelia will colonize the entire paddy straw bag within 15 days. Now the polythene cover is peeled off and the compact lump of paddy straw is placed in a cool shady room and sprayed with water 3-4 times per day. The young fruit bodies will come out from the bag. When the fruit bodies attain full growth, they could be harvested.

FACTORS AFFECTING MUSHROOM CULTIVATION

Successful cultivation of mushroom depends on many factors such as, temperature, relative humidity, moisture content of substrate, air ventilation in mushroom house quality of substrate and spawn etc.

Temperature

The optimum temperature for mycelia and vegetative growth of oyster mushroom, the required temperature is 23-28°C during spawn running or vegetative growth. Rising temperature should be checked through water. Temperature required for paddy straw mushroom is around 30°C. In case of white button mushroom, when the mycelium covers the casing soil 10 days after casing, temperature should be reduced to 14 to 18°C for fruit formation and this temperature should be maintained throughout the growth of the crop. Temperature required for reproductive stage of oyster mushroom is 20 to 30°C. Beyond this temperature the fruiting of oyster mushroom reduces.

Relative humidity

In general, mushrooms require high relative humidity during spawn running. During cropping period, high humidity (more than 80-90%) results in the incidence of bacterial blotch whereas lower than optimum relative humidity result in reduction in yield. During dry season, fresh air should be introduced to maintain temperature. Watering is done frequently particularly on walls, floor and also wet gunny bags are to be hung on the windows so that the humidity of the room may be increased.

Moisture Content

Maintaining appropriate moisture during cultivation of mushroom is an important factor. It is essential to maintain moisture especially during vegetative and reproductive phases of mushroom cultivation.

Mushroom crop should be protected from dry atmosphere. However, the moisture content of substrate should be 68-70%. Direct application of water on bed is more or less injurious to growing crops. In case of polythene bags, moisture content should be 65-68%. In beds, watering depends on the atmospheric condition of mushroom house. At this stage, no ventilation is required to maintain moist atmosphere, but the walls and floor should be kept wet which reduces water loss from the substrate.

Ventilation

Ventilation is one of the important factors for mushroom cultivation. Ventilation is required for maintaining suitable environmental condition and removal of toxic gas by introduction of adequate fresh air. During spawn running, little ventilation is required which is well enough to change the air from the room. 4% carbon dioxide is required for good spawn growth.

Ventilation should be increased after spawn run. Low concentration of carbon dioxide (0.2%) during cropping produced abnormalities in mushroom crop and if carbon dioxide concentration is too high, mushroom appears with too thick stalk and too small cap. High speed of air causes scale formation and cracks in caps particularly, when relative humidity is low.

Good spawn

Spawn means the vegetative mycelia growth of mushroom on suitable substrate. For the good cultivation of mushroom, spawn must be of strain originating from single specimen or of a perfect crop. Substrate must be uniformly covered with white mycelium. It should be free from all contaminations like moulds and other microorganisms. Appearance of dark green brown and black patches in mushroom bottles indicates the contaminated mushroom. Fresh spawn has a strong mushroom odour, dried mushroom is 8.h odorless. However, through examination and test establishes the condition of mushroom whether it is good or bad.

Good Substrate

The mushroom bed preparing substrates (Paddy straw) should be uncoupled fresh, not more than one year old, and not very leafy and it should be stored at a proper place so that it does not get wet during rain. It is colonized unwanted microbes. These microbes completely affect or reduced the yield of mushroom during the cultivation period.

Preparation of Plant Extracts for Phytochemical Screening

The fresh plant samples (Plant leaves) were collected and washed under running tap water and dried an oven at 40^oc for 3 days. The dried plant materials were ground into powder. About 10 g of dry powered plant material was extracted by soxhlate apparatus using methanol, chloroform and water solvent. Extracts was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator and the concentrated residual extracts were stored at 4^oc in a dry airtight container until further use.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of *Pleurotus florida*

Preliminary Phytochemical analysis was carried out for Aqueous and ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* as per standard methods described by Ebana *et al.*, 2014; 2015 and Preveena *et al.*, 2014 but with some little modifications.

Test for alkaloids (Wagner's reagent):

A fraction of extracts was treated with 3-5 drops of Wagner's reagent (1.27g of iodine And 2g of potassium iodine in 100 ml of water) and observed for the formation of reddish brown precipitate indicate the presence of alkaloids.

Test for Flavonoids (Alkaline reagent test):

2 ml of extracts was treated with few drops of 20% sodium hydroxide solution. Formation of intense yellow color which become colorless on addition of dilute hydrochloric acid, indicate the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Sterols (Liebermann-Burchard test):

1ml of extract was treated with drop of chloroform acetic anhydride and 1ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ and observed for the formation of dark pink or red color.

Test for Tannins (Braymer's test):

Two ml of extract was treated with 10% alcoholic ferric chloride solution and observed for the formation of blue or greenish color solution.

Test for Saponins:

Exactly 2 ml of distilled water was added to 2 ml of the aqueous extract and shaken for about 5 to 10 minutes. Formation of about 1 cm layer of permanent froth was regarded as positive.

Test for Phenols (Ferric chloride test):

A fraction of the extracts was treated with aqueous 5% ferric chloride and observed for the formation of deep blue or black color.

Test for Terpenoids (Salkowki's test):

One ml of chloroform was added to 2ml of each extract followed by a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. A reddish brown precipitate produced immediately indicate the presence of terpenoids.

Test for Cardiac glycosides (Keller kelliiani's test):

5ml of extract was treated with 2 ml of glacial acetic acid in test tube and a drop of ferric chloride solution was added to it. This was carefully underplayed with 1ml concentrated sulphuric acid. A brown ring at the interface indicated the presence of deoxysugar characteristic of cardenolides. A violet ring may appear below the ring while in the acetic acid layer, a greenish ring may from indicate the presence of glycosides.

Test for Anthraquinones:

About 2 ml of each extracts were shaken with 10ml of benzene, these were filtered and 5 ml of 10% ammonia solution added to the filtrates and the mixtures stired. The presence of a pink or red or violet coloration in the lower phase indicated the presence of free anthraquinones.

Test for Phlobatannins (Precipitate test):

Deposition of red precipitate when 2 ml of extracts was boiled with 1 ml of 1% aqueous hydrochloric acid was taken as evidence for the presence of phlobatannins.

Test for Quinones:

One ml of extract was treated with concentrated HCL and observed for the formation of yellow precipitate.

RESULTS

The present study was carried out cultivation and analyze of preliminary phytochemical screening of Oyster mushroom of *Pleurotus florida* using agricultural wastes of paddy straw.

Cultivation of *Pleurotus florida*

Mushroom is an attractive crop to cultivate in developing countries for many reasons. Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus florida*) cultivation has increased tremendously throughout the world during the last few decades, Oyster mushroom accounted for 14.2% of the total world production of edible mushroom. *P. florida* was successfully grown on PDA. The oyster mushroom completely covered the petriplates in 9 days and its color and appearance looks like pure cotton (Fig. 1).

Fig 1: Mycelial growth of *Pleurotus Florida*.

Pleurotus florida behaved drastically on different growing media in completing their mycelial growth and treatment variety interaction was highly significant. Paddy straw was taken mycelia growth between 18 and 25 days respectively to complete mycelial growth. *Pleurotus florida* behaved significantly of growing PDA media to attain harvesting stage. *Pleurotus florida* were grown in room temperature i.e. 24 °C. The humidity and water were spraying on *Pleurotus florida* on paddy straw. Cultivation the growth was observed in raw materials in 18-25 days and first harvest can be made on 19th day itself it implies that the growth of the mushroom. From the observation, pH (6.5), Temperature (25– 30^oC), Crop cycle (35 – 50 days) and First Harvest(19th day), Yield/bed (1kg) and Fruiting body (1.183 ± 0.008) were represented in the (Table 1).

Table1: Optimization condition of *Pleurotus florida*.

Character	<i>Pleurotus florida</i>
Substrate	Paddy straw
pH	6.5
Temperature	25– 30 ^o C
Crop cycle	35 – 50 days
Fruiting Body	1.183± 0.008
First Harvest	19 th day
Yield/bed	1 kg

± Standard deviation (SD).

Fig 2: Mother spawn of *Pleurotus florida*.

Fig 3: Sterilized substrate of paddy straw.

Fig 4: Spawning of paddy straw bed.

Fig 5: Fruiting bodies of *Pleurotus florida* on paddy straw.

Fig 6: Dry Powder of *Pleurotus florida*.

Fig 7: Preparation of extract by soxhlate.

Preliminary Phytochemical activity of *Pleurotus florida*

The present study was carried out in preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Pleurotus florida*. The ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* revealed the presence of medicinally important bioactive ingredients. The aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found to contain alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids and cardiac glycosides. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* showed, the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins and steroids (Figure. 8). The aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found of absence of some phytochemicals compounds such as phenols, saponins, tannins, quinines, pholobatannins and anthroquinones. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found of absence of some phytochemicals compounds such as phenols, tannins, pholobatannins, Cardiac glycosides and anthroquinones (Figure. 9). The Phytochemical characters of *Pleurotus florida* of water and ethanol extract investigated were summarized in the (Table 2).

Table 2: Qualitative Phytochemical analysis of *Pleurotus florida*:

Phytochemicals	Observations	Extracts	
		Aqueous	Ethanol
Alkaloids	Cream color	+	+
Wagner's test	Reddish brown solution/ precipitate		
Flavonoids	Formation of intense yellow color	+	+
Alkaline reagent test			
Phenols	Deep blue to Black color formation	-	-
Ferric chloride test	White precipitate		
Terpenoids	Reddish brown precipitate	+	+
Salkowski test			
Saponin	Stable persistent	-	+
Froth test			
Steroids	Formation of dark pink or red color	+	+
Liebermann-Burchard test			
Tannins	Formation of blue or greenish color	-	-
Braymer's test			
Pholobatannins	Red precipitate	-	-
Precipitate test			
Anthroquinones	pink or red or violet colouration	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	Formation of greenish ring	+	-
Keller kelliani's test			
Quinones	Yellow color precipitate	-	-

+: Present; -: absent.

Fig 8: Preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Pleurotus florida* in ethanol extract.

Fig 9: Preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Pleurotus florida* in aqueous extract.

DISCUSSION

The present study was carried out cultivation and analyze of preliminary Phytochemical screening of Oyster mushroom of *Pleurotus florida* using agricultural wastes of paddy straw.

Cultivation of *Pleurotus florida*

Mushroom is an attractive crop to cultivate in developing countries for many reasons. Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus florida*) cultivation has increased tremendously throughout the world during the last few decades, Oyster mushroom accounted for 14.2% of the total world production of edible mushroom. *P. florida* was successfully grown on PDA. The oyster mushroom completely covered the petriplates in 9 days and its color and appearance looks like pure cotton (Fig. 1). Like as the present study concluded that *Pleurotus florida* can be cultivated by different type of lignocellulosic substrate and among those reeds was a best alternative and replacement of traditional substrates. The spent mushroom substrates as casing yield of *Pleurotus florida*. The present study further leads us to cultivate and commercialize the *Pleurotus florida* production using reeds for the benefit of society (Karuppuraj et al., 2014). Described the cultivation of oyster mushroom using different lignocellulosic substrates and found that pinhead formations take place after 7-8 days while sporocarps formation take place after 10-12 days of spawn running (Khan et al., 2001).

Pleurotus florida behaved drastically on different growing media in completing their mycelial growth and treatment variety interaction was highly significant. Paddy straw was taken mycelial growth between 15 and 25 days respectively to complete mycelial growth. *Pleurotus florida* behaved significantly of growing PDA media to attain harvesting stage. *Pleurotus florida* were grown in room temperature i.e. 24 °C. The humidity and water were spraying on *Pleurotus florida* on paddy straw. Cultivation the growth was observed in raw materials in 18-25 days and first harvest can be made on 19th day itself it implies that the growth of the mushroom. From the observation, pH (6.5), Temperature (25– 30°C), Crop cycle (35 – 50 days) and First Harvest (19th day), Yield/bed (1kg) and Fruiting body (1.183 ± 0.008) were represented in the Table –1.

The time required for harvest of the fruiting bodies on soybean straw always preceded paddy straw alone or in combination (Syed Abrar Ahmed *et al.*, 2009). This result same as the results indicated that the spawn running was completed in the bags 10 to 14 days and pinheads appeared on the 19th-20th. Pinheads turned into leaf like 23rd day and the first harvest was made at about 26-28 days. The second harvest will be another 4 or 5 days (Borchers *et al.*, 2004). The total yield of *Pleurotus florida* in terms of fresh weight was 536.44 g/kg dry substrate and dry weight was 71.6 g/kg dry substrate (Fahad Alkoaik *et al.*, 2015).

Preliminary Phytochemical activity of *Pleurotus Florida*

The present study was carried out in preliminary Phytochemical analysis of *Pleurotus florida*. The ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* revealed the presence of medicinally important bioactive ingredients. The aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found to contain alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids and cardiac glycosides. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* showed, the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins and steroids (Figure. 8). The aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found of absence of some phytochemicals compounds such as phenols, saponins, tannins, quinines, phlobatannins and anthroquinones. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* was found of absence of some phytochemicals compounds such as phenols, tannins, phlobatannins, Cardiac glycosides and anthroquinones (Figure.9). The phytochemical characters of *Pleurotus florida* of water and ethanol extract investigated were summarized in the Table.2.

Similarly, Theethanolic and aqueous extracts of the oyster mushroom showed that it is rich in number of phytochemical bases such as alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, flavonoids, reducing compounds and polyphenols. However, the extracts lacked phlobatannins, anthraquinones and hydroxymethylanthraquinones (Akyuz *et al.*, 2010). The phytochemical analysis conducted on the *Pleurotus* strains showed that they are rich in phenols, flavonoids, carotenoids and mineral element. These phytochemicals have also been observed in mushrooms by other workers. In the present study, the trend for total, every strain has its own unique mechanisms in the synthesis and metabolism of these phytochemicals (Mary Obadai *et al.*, 2014). The total phenol contents in the present study were lower than what they observed, however the total flavonoid contents of three of the *Pleurotus* strains compared favourably with those of the Macroplepiotoid mushrooms (Arbaayah and Umi Kalsom, 2013).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The mushrooms belong to *Pleurotus spp.* were highly diversified group and distributed world-wide. Almost all mushrooms belong to this species were edible and used in different culture as potential source of food and medicines. In the present investigation was carried out on cultivation of *Pleurotus florida* and screening of preliminary phytochemicals. *Pleurotus florida* was cultivated on sterilized paddy straw. Environmental factors of pH (6.5) and temperature (25– 30°C) were maintained between mycelia growth to attain harvesting stage. Cultivation of the growth was observed in raw materials in 18-25 days and first harvest can be made on 19th day itself it implies that the growth of the mushroom. Total yield was one kg for one bed. Preliminary phytochemical compounds were screened of *Pleurotus florida* with different extract of aqueous and ethanol solvent. Alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids and cardiac glycosides were presence in aqueous extract of *Pleurotus florida*. Whereas ethanol extract of *Pleurotus florida* was contain alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins and steroids. Some phytochemical ingredients Phenols, tannins, phlobatannins and anthroquinones were absence in both extracts. Further study can be aimed at to identify the bioactive compounds and determine the cultivation of *Pleurotus florida* on paddy Straw.

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